

DETERMINANTS OF HOUSEHOLD PURCHASING DECISIONS AND EXPENDITURE ON POULTRY MEAT IN GWAGWALADA AREA COUNCIL, FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Poultry meat is an important source of affordable animal protein in Nigeria, yet household consumption patterns vary widely due to socioeconomic and market-related factors. This study analyzes the determinants of household purchasing decisions and expenditure on poultry meat in Gwagwalada Area Council, Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria. Primary data were collected from 140 households using a structured questionnaire through a multi-stage sampling technique. Descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized. Results show that (88.6%) of households purchased poultry meat within the last 30 days, with a mean monthly expenditure of ₦9,751.43. Using the Heckman two-stage selection model to correct for potential selection bias, the results reveals that age was significant at ($p \leq 0.10$) and influenced the decision to purchase poultry meat. Also, household size was significant at ($p \leq 0.05$) and had a negative effect on expenditure on poultry meat, while market access was significant at ($p \leq 0.10$), and health-related motivations ($p \leq 0.01$) positively influenced expenditure on poultry meat. Major constraints to poultry meat consumption included high perishability, food safety concerns, low income, and inadequate access to information. The study concludes that improving market access, strengthening cold-chain infrastructure, and promoting nutrition education could enhance poultry meat consumption and dietary quality among households.

Keywords: Poultry meat, Expenditure, Income, Purchasing decision, Heckman selection model.

JEL Codes: Q1, Q12

1. INTRODUCTION

Poultry production is one of the fastest-growing agricultural subsectors in Nigeria, playing a pivotal role in addressing protein deficits and supporting livelihoods. The industry is among the largest in Africa, with an estimated population of 180 million birds, and has experienced

strong, often double-digit expansion in recent years (Food and Agriculture Organization [FAO], 2019). The poultry subsector is recognized for its role in improving rural and peri-urban livelihoods and lowering the country's protein deficit; industry and policy assessments show that poultry contributes significantly to agricultural value added and supports millions of jobs in production, processing, and distribution (Otitoju & Gbadebo, 2025). The swift growth is propelled by hastening urbanization and increasing per capita demand for affordable animal protein, which collectively have heightened household dependence on poultry meat as an accessible source of high-quality nutrition. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2023, Offor, Osondu, & Okolo, 2024). Beyond direct agricultural output, the production of poultry meat has wider welfare ramifications for Nigerian households (Arua, Muomaiife, & Ibe (2025). The national food- supply data and sector reviews indicate poultry (often counted together with eggs) supplies a substantial share of animal- source protein, and this can be attributed to the short production cycles, faster returns on investments compared to the ruminants, generally lower retail prices, and broad cultural acceptability, which together raise poultry's accessibility across income groups (FAO, 2024). The industry's multiplier effect stimulates related sectors such as feed production, veterinary services, cold chain infrastructure, and retail markets, thereby creating cascading economic benefits throughout the food system. Poultry meat is a high- quality source of animal protein that supplies all essential amino acids required for growth and immune function. The lean poultry cuts, particularly skinless chicken breast, contain substantially less total and saturated fat than many red- meat cuts and provide significant amounts of niacin, vitamin B₆, selenium, phosphorus and zinc (Selvan, 2024). Despite these benefits and the increased availability of poultry meat, household purchase decisions remain influenced by a complex interaction of socioeconomic and behavioural factors such as income levels, household size, price fluctuations and expansion of modern retail outlets. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the determinants of household purchasing decisions and expenditure on poultry meat in Gwagwalada Area Council, Federal Capital Territory. The findings will provide empirical evidence to guide stakeholders in the poultry value chain, policymakers, and nutrition advocates in developing strategies that enhance household access to affordable, nutritious poultry products while supporting the sustainable growth of Nigeria's poultry industry. The broad objective was to examine the determinants for purchasing decisions and expenditure of poultry meat among households in Gwagwalada Area Council, Federal Capital Territory. The specific objectives are to: describe the socio-economic characteristics of the households in the study area; estimate the purchasing decisions and expenditure on poultry meat among the households in the study area; analyze the factors associated with the purchasing decisions and expenditure on poultry meat among the households in the study area and identify constraints against poultry meat consumption among the households in the study area.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Poultry meat consumption plays a vital role in improving household nutrition and addressing protein deficiencies, particularly in developing countries where access to affordable animal-source foods remains limited. Poultry meat is widely preferred due to its relatively low price, short production cycle, cultural acceptability, and favorable nutritional profile, including high-quality protein and lower saturated fat compared to red meat (FAO, 2023; Connolly & Campbell, 2023). In Nigeria, rising urbanization and income diversification have increased demand for poultry meat, especially among peri-urban households (Onyenekwe, Amaechina, Onah, Ayogu, & Eze, 2025).

Empirical studies indicate that household socioeconomic characteristics such as income, education, household size, and age significantly influence poultry meat consumption and expenditure. While higher income and education levels generally increase animal protein consumption, larger household sizes often constrain percapita expenditure due to budgetary pressures (Daba, Murimi, Abegaz, & Hailu, 2021). Market-related factors, including access to markets and transportation infrastructure, also play a crucial role by reducing transaction costs and improving food availability and diversity (Usman & Haile, 2022).

Health awareness has emerged as an important behavioral driver of poultry meat consumption, as consumers increasingly associate poultry with healthier diets and disease prevention. However, constraints such as perishability, inadequate cold storage, food safety concerns, and information gaps continue to limit consumption in tropical settings. These studies underscore the need for integrated market, nutrition, and infrastructure interventions to enhance poultry meat consumption and household welfare.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Theoretical frameworks provide a structured lens through which to analyze the determinants of household purchasing decisions and expenditure on poultry meat in Gwagwalada Area Council, Nigeria. This study is built on the theory of household decisions.

2.1.1 Theory of Households' Decisions

The Theory of household decision is a fundamental concept in economics that seeks to explain how individuals and households make decisions about the allocation of their limited resources among various goods and services to maximize their satisfaction or utility (Varian, 2014). It provides valuable insights into the decision-making process behind household purchasing decisions and expenditure on products such as poultry meat in Gwagwalada Area Council. The Key Concepts within the Theory of Household Decisions are:

Utility: Utility refers to the satisfaction or happiness that individuals derive from purchasing goods and services. In the context of poultry meat consumption decision, utility can be seen as the pleasure and well-being households gain from including poultry in their diets. Households aim to maximize their total utility when making consumption decisions.

Budget Constraint: Every household faces a budget constraint, which represents the limited amount of income available to spend on goods and services. The budget constraint is a critical factor in poultry meat consumption decisions, as households must allocate their income efficiently to meet their needs and preferences.

Preferences and Indifference Curves: Preferences are subjective and unique to each household. Indifference curves are graphical representations of different combinations of goods and services that provide the same level of utility or satisfaction to a consumer. In the context of poultry meat, indifference curves can illustrate how households trade off between poultry meat and other goods based on their preferences.

Marginal Utility: Marginal utility is the additional satisfaction gained from consuming one more unit of a good or service while keeping other consumption constant. It is a crucial concept

in households' decisions as it helps households decide whether to increase or decrease their consumption of poultry meat based on its marginal utility relative to its price.

In Gwagwalada Area Council, the Theory of households' decisions can shed light on why and how households make decisions regarding poultry meat consumption. Households aim to maximize their overall satisfaction or utility by allocating their limited resources effectively. They evaluate the utility derived from purchasing poultry meat in terms of taste, nutritional value, and other factors. The income level of households in the area council determines their budget constraint. Households must decide how much of their income they are willing to expended on poultry meat purchase while considering other essential needs.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 The Study Area and Data

This study was conducted in Gwagwalada Area Council, Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria, which is located between longitudes 6°45' and 7°30' east of the Greenwich Meridian and latitudes 8°45' and 9°10' north of the equator. The Federal Capital Territory (FCT) comprises six Area Councils, with Gwagwalada Area Council being one of the most prominent (Aluko, Sennuga, & Ezinne, 2021). Gwagwalada Area Council serves as a major suburban settlement within the FCT and encompasses several communities, including Gwagwalada town, Tunga-Maje, Kutunku, Ibwa, Paiko, Ikwa, Tungan-Maje and Dobi. The area experiences a tropical climate with an average annual temperature ranging between 28°C and 35°C, with peak temperatures occurring in March and April. The average annual rainfall is approximately 1,500mm to 1,600mm, with about 65% of the yearly precipitation occurring between June and September during the rainy season, Nigerian Meteorological Agency [NiMet] (2023). The entire region lies within the Guinea Savannah vegetation zone, characterized by favorable climatic conditions and fertile soil properties that support diverse agricultural activities. Agriculture remains one of the principal economic activities in Gwagwalada Area Council, with crop cultivation including maize, cassava, yams, rice, vegetables, and soybeans. Beyond crop production, the indigenous population engages in livestock farming (particularly poultry, cattle, and small ruminants), fish farming, petty trading, and civil service employment. The area's proximity to Abuja city centre has also stimulated commercial activities, making it an important market hub for agricultural produce and livestock products, including poultry meat (Dutse, Egwuma, Dodo, Danladi, & Iliya, 2024)

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed for this study. In the first stage, Gwagwalada Area Council was purposively selected from the Area Councils in the Federal Capital Territory due to its high level of agricultural activities, including poultry meat. In the second stage, four wards, Gwagwalada Central, Kutunku, Dobi, and Zuba, were randomly selected from the ten political wards in the Area Council. Finally, 140 households were randomly selected.

This study used primary sources for its data. Using a well-designed questionnaire, the researcher and trained enumerators collected the data.

3.2 Model specification

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to achieve the objectives of this study. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the socio-economic characteristics of the households and to estimate the purchasing decisions and expenditure on poultry meat among the households. (e.g frequency and percentages). Hechman two-stage selection model was used to analyse the factors influencing the household purchasing decisions and the expenditure on

poultry meat; and factor analyses was used to identify the constraints against the consumption of poultry meat among the household in the study area. The Heckman two-stage selection model, while objective (iv) was addressed using factor analysis. The Heckman Two-Stage Selection Model is used for possible sample selection bias that may arise if the decision to participate in a programme or adopt a practice is not random but influenced by observable and unobservable factors (Heckman, 1979). Heckman selection model has been used in studies by Otitoju and Olawoye (2026), Otitoju, Olaifa and Obasanya (2022), and Popoola, Otitoju and Tanko (2016). In this research, it is the purchasing decisions and expenditure of poultry meat among households in the study area.

Stage One: Selection Equation

In the first stage, a probit model was estimated to determine the probability of deciding to purchase poultry meat.

The selection equation is specified as:

$$PD_i^* = Z_i' \gamma + u_i \tag{1}$$

$$PD_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } PD_i^* > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } PD_i^* \leq 0 \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

where:

PD_i^* is the latent variable representing the i -th household.

γ is the parameter

Z_i is a vector of explanatory variables for the i -th household influencing the decision to participate.

$u_i \sim N(0,1)$

The first stage produces the inverse Mills ratio (IMR), which captures the effect of selection bias.

$IMR_i = \phi(PD_i^*) / \Phi(PD_i^*)$ for a household with $PD_i = 1$

$IMR_i = -\phi(PD_i^*) / [1 - \Phi(PD_i^*)]$ for a household with $PD_i = 0$

Where ϕ and Φ are the probability density and cumulative functions of the standard normal distribution, respectively.

Stage Two: Outcome Equation

In the second stage, the outcome equation estimates the respondent's expenditure on poultry meat using the subsample of households who decided to purchase poultry meat.

$$Y_i = X_i' \beta + \epsilon_i \tag{3}$$

Where:

Y_i is the outcome of interest (only observed when $PD = 1$)

X_i is a vector of explanatory variables

β are parameters

$$\varepsilon_{1t} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

The control variables used include.

X₁=Age (years)

X₂= Sex (1 if male, 0 = female)

X₃= Years of Schooling (years)

X₄= Household size (number of persons in the household)

X₅= Household Income (Naira)

X₆= Access to market (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X₇= Distance to the market (km)

X₈= Storage facility (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X₉= Possession of Refrigerator (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X₁₀= Purchase poultry meat for health reason (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents in the Study Area

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents include their age, household size, educational level, sex of the respondents, income, market access, storage, and possession of a refrigerator. In the Gwagwalada Area Council, the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents were summarized in Table 1.

As presented in Table 1, the result shows that the majority, 64.3% of the respondents, were male, while 35.7% of the respondents were female. This indicates that men headed most households in the study area. This reflects entrenched socio-cultural norms in Nigeria, where men traditionally control productive resources such as land and capital. This finding is consistent with the findings of Olohungebe, Olawoye, and Abdulkareem (2025) and Obi-Egbedi and Owosho (2023), who reported a disparity between males and females resulting from the labour-intensive nature of agricultural production. For the marital status, the majority of the respondents (52.9%) were married, followed by single (35.7%), widowed (5.7%), and divorced (5.7%). This result conforms to the findings of Taiga, Adofu, and Ugwuoke (2023), who reported that majority of sampled respondents were married in Kogi State, Nigeria. The Educational level of the respondents in the study area shows that about (78.6%) had a tertiary education, while (2.1%) of the respondents never attended formal education. This reflects the semi-urban nature of Gwagwalada Area Council and its proximity to Abuja. Higher educational attainment enhances farmers' ability to adopt improved technologies, access market information, and engage with extension services effectively and efficiently. This finding agrees with Alabi, Oladele, and Oladele (2020), who reported that a higher education level can facilitate the adoption of new technology. The result also indicates that the majority (49.3%) of the respondents fell within the age range of 21-30 years, 20.7% whose age is within 31-40 years, 15.7% with the age range of 41-50 years, 6.4% with the age range of 51-60 years, 5.0% fell to the age range of 61-70, 2.1% with the age range of 71-80, 0.7% less than or equal to 20 and a mean age of approximately 35 years, indicating that most of the farmers are in their economically active and productive age bracket. The household size result shows that 53.6% of the respondents fell within the range of 1-5, followed by respondents 43.6% whose ranges between 6-10, 2.9% ranges between 11-15 and the average household size of 6 persons per household. The findings reveal that the majority of respondents (37.5%) earned between ₦50,001 and ₦100,000, followed by 31.4% who reported incomes in the ₦10,001–₦50,000 range, while 16.4% fell within ₦100,001–₦150,000; smaller proportions included 4.3% in the ₦150,001–₦200,000 bracket, 2.1% each in the ₦200,001–₦250,000 and ₦450,001–₦500,000

ranges, 1.4% spread across ₦300,001–₦350,000, ₦350,001–₦400,000, ₦400,001–₦450,000, and ₦600,001–₦650,000, while only 0.7% earned ₦10,000 or less and another 0.7% earned between ₦550,001 and ₦600,000. The result further indicates ₦115,635.71 as the average household monthly income. Furthermore, the majority of the respondents (97.1%) had market access, while (2.9%) of them had no access to the market. This indicates road connectivity to major urban markets, facilitating input procurement. High ownership of storage facilities (87.1%) and refrigerators (67.9%) indicates relatively better handling capacity and food preservation practices. Access to storage and cold facilities reduces food wastage, stabilizes income, and enhances food security.

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents in the Study Area

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean
Male	90	64.3	
Female	50	35.7	
Marital status			
Single	50	35.7	
Married	74	52.9	
Widowed/Widower	8	5.7	
Divorced	8	5.7	
Level of Education			
No formal education	3	2.1	
Attended primary school	9	6.4	16.08
Attended secondary school	18	12.9	
Attended tertiary school	110	78.6	
Age			
≤20	1	0.7	
21 – 30	69	49.3	
31 – 40	29	20.7	
41 – 50	22	15.7	35 years
51 – 60	9	6.4	
61 – 70	7	5.0	
71 – 80	3	2.1	
Household Size (Number)			
1- 5	75	53.6	
6 – 10	61	43.6	6 persons
11- 15	4	2.9	
Household Monthly Income			
No Income	1	0.7	
Less than 10,000.00	1	0.7	
10,001.00 – 50,000.00	44	31.4	
50,001.00 – 100,000.00	50	37.5	₦115,635.7143
100,001.00 – 150,000.00	23	16.4	
150,001.00 – 200,000.00	6	4.3	
200,001.00 – 250,000.00	3	2.1	
300,001.00 – 350,000.00	2	1.4	
350,001.00 – 400,000.00	2	1.4	
400,001.00 – 450,000.00	2	1.4	
450,001.00 – 500,000.00	3	2.1	

550,001.00 – 600,000.00	1	0.7
600,001.00 – 650,000.00	2	1.4
Market Access		
No access	4	2.9
Access	136	97.1
Storage		
No	18	12.9
Yes	122	87.1
Possession of a Refrigerator		
No	45	32.1
Yes	95	67.9
Total	140	100.0

Source: Computed from field data, 2023.

4.2 Purchasing Decisions and Expenditure on Poultry Meat among the Households in the Study Area

Table 2 presents the distribution of households’ purchasing decisions and expenditure on poultry meat in the study area. The results show that a substantial majority of the households (88.6%) reported purchasing poultry meat, while only 11.4% did not make any purchase during the reference period of the last 30 days. This high level of participation suggests that poultry meat is an important component of household diets in the study area. Poultry meat is widely preferred due to its affordability relative to red meat, ease of preparation, and perceived health benefits, particularly its lower fat content and high-quality protein. These findings align with Dutse et al. (2024).

The expenditure pattern further indicates varying levels of consumption among households. About (36.4%) of the respondents spent less than ₦5,000 on poultry meat in the last 30 days, while (27.1%) spent between ₦5,000 and ₦10,000. This apparent discrepancy suggests that households may not necessarily purchase poultry meat, but households may have obtained poultry meat through non-market sources, including gifts, ceremonies, or their own production (backyard poultry), which would reduce reported expenditure despite positive consumption responses. These finding is consistent with Izekor and Kadri (2025), who reported that non-market sources are common sources of poultry meat consumption. A smaller proportion of households reported higher levels of expenditure, with 12.1% spending between ₦10,001 and ₦15,000 and 7.9% spending between ₦15,001 and ₦20,000. Only a few households spent above ₦20,000, indicating that frequent or bulk purchase of poultry meat may reflect relatively higher-income households.

The mean monthly expenditure on poultry meat (₦9,751.43) reflects moderate consumption levels and aligns with the semi-urban nature of the study area, where households combine market purchases with other protein sources such as fish, eggs, and plant-based proteins. The 11.4% of households with no expenditure may rely on alternative protein sources, home-reared poultry, or may be constrained by low purchasing power, as observed in similar urban-rural interface settings.

Decisions and Expenditure on Poultry Meat among the Households in the Study Area

Poultry Meat	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Purchasing Decision			
No	16	11.4	

Yes	124	88.6
Expenditure on Poultry meat (Last 30 days)		9751.4286
No Expenditure	16	11.43
Less than 5,000.00	51	36.4
10,001.00 – 15,000.00	17	12.1
15,001.00 – 20,000.00	11	7.9
20,001.00 – 25,000.00	2	1.4
25,001.00 – 30,000.00	3	2.1
5,000.00 – 10,000.00	38	27.1
45,000.00 – 50,000.00	1	0.7
Total	140	100.0

Source: Computed from field data, 2023.

4.3 Determinants of Household Purchasing Decisions and Expenditure on Poultry Meat

The Heckman selection model was employed to account for potential sample selection bias arising from households that do not purchase poultry meat. The model consists of two equations: the selection equation examining factors influencing the decision to participate in poultry meat purchasing, and the outcome equation analyzing determinants of expenditure on poultry meat among households. The diagnostic statistics reveal 140 total observations, with 15 censored and 125 uncensored households. The insignificant Mills Lambda ($p=0.312$) indicated no sample selection bias. Also, the non-significant Wald chi-square ($\chi^2=10.58$, $p=0.3914$) revealed limited overall model explanatory power, implying that unmeasured factors such as price dynamics, quality perceptions, and cultural preferences likely play important roles in determining household poultry meat expenditure.

The selection equation examines factors influencing households' decision to purchase poultry meat, and only one variable was significant. The age of the household head demonstrated a positive and significant relationship with participation, 0.0049, indicating an increasing likelihood of purchasing poultry meat. This may reflect accumulated purchasing power, established dietary preferences, or greater nutritional awareness associated with age. These finding is consistent with Izeke et al. (2025).

The outcome equation analyses determinants of expenditure on poultry meat among participating households. The variables significant were Household size, Market access, and Purchasing poultry meat for health reasons. Household size exhibited a negative relationship with poultry meat expenditure, indicating that these households were willing to expend -0.17 less units less on poultry meat. Contrary to the conventional expectation that larger families would purchase more protein, this result likely reflects budget constraints, where larger households must distribute limited food budgets across more individuals, potentially leading to

reduce per capita expenditure on relatively expensive protein sources like poultry meat. These findings are consistent with Daba et al. (2021), who found that larger family size was negatively associated with household-level consumption of animal source foods (including poultry and meat). Market access had a positive relationship with expenditure on poultry meat. Households with better access to markets spent approximately 1.68 units more on poultry meat. Households located closer to markets tend to spend more on total food consumption and have better diet quality because improved market access reduces transaction costs, increases food variety availability, and encourages greater reliance on market purchases. This result is consistent with Usman and Haile (2022). Purchasing poultry meat for health reasons also had a positive relationship with expenditure on poultry meat. Households purchasing poultry meat for health reasons spent approximately 1.32 units more on poultry meat. This finding highlights the critical role of nutritional awareness and health consciousness in driving protein consumption patterns. Health-motivated consumers likely possess greater knowledge of poultry meat's nutritional benefits, including high-quality protein, essential amino acids, and favorable fat profiles and are willing to allocate larger portions of their food budget accordingly. This finding is consistent with Connolly and Campbell (2023), who highlight poultry meat's role as a high-quality source of complete protein and essential nutrients, supporting healthy dietary outcomes.

Table 3: Heckman results on factors associated with the purchasing decisions and expenditure on poultry meat among the households in the study

Explanatory Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	z-value	P> z
Poultry meat Purchase				
Age(Years)	0.0049	0.0026	1.86*	0.062
Sex	0.0269	0.0489	0.55	0.582
Years of Schooling	-0.00685	0.00827	-0.83	0.408
Household size	-0.00285	0.01235	-0.23	0.817
Household Income	-2.87e-07	2.48e-07	-1.15	0.248
Market Access	-0.08727	0.2060	-0.42	0.672
Distance	0.00641	0.0225	0.28	0.776
Storage	.070630	0.0921	-0.79	0.429
Refrigerator	-0.0490	0.90044	0.66	0.510
Purchase Poultry meat for Health reason	0.0595	0.09044	0.66	0.510
Constant	0.9746	0.295	3.30	0.001
Expended Poultry meat (30days)				
Age(Years)	-0.0116	0.0217	-0.53	0.593
Sex	-0.0765	0.392	-0.20	0.845
Years of Schooling	0.0472	0.133	0.36	0.722
Sch ²	0.000523	0.00563	0.09	0.926
Household size	-0.17041	0.0820	-2.08**	0.038
Household Income	3.91e-06	3.40e-06	1.15	0.250
Market Access	1.675	0.933	1.79*	0.073
Distance	-0.149	0.173	-0.86	0.389
Storage	-1.165	0.833	-1.40	0.162
Refrigerator	-0.201	0.461	-0.44	0.663
Purchase Poultry meat for Health reason	1.316	0.417	3.16***	0.002

Constant	0.807	1.591	0.51	0.612
Mills				
Lambda	-0.262	0.259	-1.01	0.312
Rho	-1.00			
Sigma	0.262			

Diagnostic statistics:

Number of Observation = 140

Censored observation = 15

Uncensored observation = 125

Wald chi2 (7) =10.58

Prob > chi2 =0.3914

*** (1% significance level); ** (5% significance level); * (10% significance level)

Source: Computed from field data, 2023

4.4 Constraints that Militates Households' Poultry Meat Consumption among Households in the Study Area

The findings in Table 4 highlight the constraints that hinder households' poultry meat consumption in the research. The major constraints faced by the respondents in the study area are easily perishability (mean = 3.04), contamination and diseases (mean = 2.98), low level of income (mean = 2.62), inadequate access to information (mean = 2.54), and cost of poultry meat (mean = 2.42). The respondents rated each constraint on an Agree scale (4 = Strongly Agree, 3 = Agree, 2 =Disagree, and 1 = Strongly Disagree); higher mean values indicate more severe challenges.

The rapid spoilage of poultry meat limits their consumption among households. This finding reflects the challenges of maintaining cold chain integrity in tropical climates and households' concerns about purchasing quantities that may deteriorate before consumption, particularly among families lacking reliable refrigeration. This result agrees with Abdullah, Al-Nabulsi, Jamama’h, Khataybeh, and Al-Ghadi (2025), who reported that perishable meats can lose quality without strict cold chain control. Similarly, safety concerns regarding contamination and diseases were also recorded. The heightened awareness likely stems from periodic avian influenza outbreaks and media reports on poultry disease incidents, which can discourage consumption. This agrees with the finding of Otekunrin, Ayinde, Otekunrin, and De Campos (2018). While income limitations constrain overall food budgets, poultry meat was perceived as relatively affordable compared to alternative protein sources such as beef and fish. Inadequate access to information about poultry meat and insufficient knowledge of health benefits suggest information asymmetries in the market, where consumers may know poultry meat exists but lack detailed nutritional knowledge or understanding of optimal storage, preparation, and consumption practices.

Other constraints faced in poultry meat consumption are that poultry meat is not well differentiated from other proteins, its taste and freshness and household illiteracy. This suggests that the households in the study area view poultry meat as interchangeable with fish, beef, or eggs, rather than possessing a unique nutritional value, but they believe poultry meat's organoleptic properties are not barriers to consumption. This agrees with Izekor et al. (2025), who reported low knowledge of food quality and listed eggs as the most consumed poultry product.

Table 5: Constraints that Militates Households' Poultry Meat Consumption among Households in the Study Area

Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean
Poultry meat is too expensive to purchase for household consumption	18(12.9)	42(30.0)	61(43.6)	19(13.6)	2.42
Households' illiteracy level	4(2.9)	15(10.7)	56(40.0)	65(46.4)	1.70
Low level of household income	24(17.1)	48(34.3)	59(42.1)	9(6.4)	2.62
The poultry meat is not readily available	5(3.6)	18(12.9)	83(59.3)	34(6.4)	1.96
Poultry meat is not well differentiated from other protein sources	19(13.6)	45(32.1)	53(37.9)	23(16.4)	2.43
Concerns about the safety of poultry meat in terms of contamination and diseases	44(31.4)	58(41.4)	29(20.7)	9(6.4)	2.98
Inadequate information on the health benefits of poultry meat	11(7.9)	37(26.4)	67(47.9)	25(17.9)	2.24
They are easily perishable	53(37.9)	49(35.0)	29(20.7)	9(6.4)	3.04
Inadequate storage facilities/refrigerator	39(27.9)	19(13.6)	39(27.9)	43(30.7)	2.39
Inadequate access to information on poultry meat	16(11.4)	60(42.9)	47(33.6)	17(12.1)	2.54
Poultry meat tastes and freshness	25(17.9)	21(15.0)	56(40.0)	38(27.1)	2.24

Source: Computed from field data, 2023.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

According to the study's findings, it was concluded that decision to purchase poultry meat is relatively high; however, household expenditure on poultry meat is significantly influenced by household size, market access, and health-related motivations. Larger household size reduced poultry meat expenditure, reflecting budget constraints, while improved market access and health consciousness increased spending. Constraints such as perishability, food safety concerns, low income, and inadequate information further limit the consumption of poultry meat. It is therefore recommended that policies should strengthen market infrastructure and cold-chain facilities to reduce spoilage and improve access. Additionally, targeted nutrition education and income-enhancing interventions could stimulate poultry meat consumption and improve household dietary quality.

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